

Classification of attributes that influence interpersonal trust in VLEs

Classification of the attributes that influence interpersonal trust among students in VLEs into themes, categories, and attributes.

Table 3
Trust attributes extracted from articles classified by category and themes

Themes	Category	Trust attributes extracted from the articles
Ability	Collaborative behavior	Collaboration; Cooperation; Discussions in forums
	Academic skills	High knowledge on a given topic; Leadership
	Socio-emotional skills	Friendliness; Socio-emotional interaction;
	Result-based	Higher Grades; hasty decisions; Low Grades
	Communication skills	Collaborative communication; Effective communication; feedback in interactions
Integrity	Ethical behavior	Ethics; Honest communication; Honesty
	Transparent behavior	Authentic emotional communication; Predictability; Sincerity;
	Egocentric behavior	Egocentrism;
	Evasive behavior	Does not assume error; Not taking responsibility;
	Commitment	Dedication; Effort; Keeping promises and commitments; Perform activities
	Reputation	Credibility; Reputation
Affinity	Similarity among users	Friends in common; Common interests; Similar interests, tastes and preferences; Similarity among users;
	Past interaction	Direct experience; Previous interaction;
NON-PERSONAL FACTORS	Second-hand trust	Experience of friends of his friends; Recommendation
	Time	elapsed time
	Non-verbal communication	Use of symbols and avatars